

PROPERTIES AND MICROSTRUCTURE OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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The microstructure and mechanical and physical properties of selected metal matrix composites have been evaluated. The composites examined had an aluminum matrix and were reinforced with alumina, graphite or silicon carbide fibers, or silicon carbide whiskers. Aluminum-silicon carbide whisker composites showed transverse strength and stiffness properties that were almost as high as the longitudinal properties. Aluminum-alumina composites had excellent fiber-matrix bonding and showed considerable modulus enhancement in all directions. Transverse strengths in aluminum-alumina composites were found to be increased by heat treatment to the level of the aluminum matrix. Poor matrix-fiber bonding was observed with aluminum-graphite composites and aluminum-silicon carbide fiber composites, resulting in a wide variation between longitudinal and transverse properties. All the metal matrix composites showed a greatly reduced longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient compared to aluminum.

1.0 MATERIALS

The following materials were tested.

- a. Al-Al₂O₃ (FP) 55% made by Du Pont
- b. Al-SiC 48% fiber made by AVCO
- c. Al-SiC 20 to 27% whiskers made by Lockheed or Silag
- d. Al-Graphite (GY70) 30% made by MCI and DWA

2.0 RESULTS

2.1 Fractography

An examination of the fracture surface of metal matrix composites reveals one of the most important features of the composite, the strength of the fiber-matrix bond. A weak interface bond results in low transverse strength and toughness and poor formability even at elevated temperatures.

An example of a fibrous composite with a good fiber-matrix bond is Al-Al₂O₃. In this composite the fiber pull out during fracture is negligible (Fig. 1), and the mechanical properties are reasonably isotropic as described below. The aluminum silicon carbide whisker composite has a matrix-whisker bond strong enough to prevent debonding during very heavy hot reduction (Fig. 2) but not strong enough to prevent whisker pull out during fracture (Fig. 3). The fact that the whiskers pull out rather than fracture indicates that the bond strength has to be improved to take advantage of the very high inherent strength in the whisker (over 7 million MPa).

At the other extreme are the aluminum-graphite composites where the fiber-matrix bond is very weak. When composites fracture, the fibers pull out a great distance and the mechanical properties are extremely anisotropic. The same problem can be encountered with composites using SiC fibers, which normally bond extremely well to aluminum. The Al-SiC fiber composites tested here used an amorphous carbon coating over the SiC fiber to improve the ease of handling. This coating caused the material to behave as if it were a graphite composite with considerable fiber pull out during fracture (Fig. 4) and a marked anisotropy of mechanical properties.

2.2 Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the composites tested are listed in Tables 1 and 2. Compared to aluminum alloys, the materials as a class have a high specific elastic modulus. Their tensile strengths along the fiber axis are similar to conventional aluminum alloys, while in many cases the tensile strengths across the fiber direction are well below those for aluminum alloys, so that cross plying is required for most structural applications. In this respect, metal matrix composites are similar to resin matrix-graphite fiber composites. The impact toughness and tensile elongation of metal matrix composites are considerably below those of conventional engineering materials, and because this difference persists at elevated temperatures, forming the materials into shapes requires techniques that are more difficult and more expensive than those used for aluminum alloys. An exception to this statement is the aluminum-silicon carbide whisker composite, which can be processed by conventional metal working equipment.

2.3 Physical Properties

The physical properties of the composites are listed in Table 3. The thermal expansion and thermal conductivity properties are significant for orbiting space structures where dimensional stability is required as the structure is thermally cycled by moving through the earth's shadow. A low coefficient of thermal expansion in the longitudinal direction (along the fiber axis) α_L and a high coefficient of thermal conductivity in the transverse direction (K_T) are desirable. It is perhaps not surprising that the transverse thermal conductivity of Al-Al₂O₃ is low because alumina is a thermal insulator; however, it is noteworthy that the transverse thermal conductivity of the aluminum-graphite composite is also low because high modulus graphite fibers have excellent thermal conductivity. This high thermal conductivity, however, is only along the fiber axis. Across the fiber axis, the thermal conductivity appears to be even lower than that of alumina, and this is reflected in the transverse conductivity measurements on the composite (Fig. 5). The thermal conductivity of the silicon carbide composites are consistent with the known high thermal conductivity of silicon carbide. Silicon carbide whiskers appear to provide about the same reduction in thermal expansion coefficient as an equal volume fraction of continuous silicon carbide fibers (Fig. 6). There are unusual problems with the dimensional stability of metal matrix composites, which are not described completely by the parameters α_L and K_T . This is because an internal stress is set up during thermal cycling that causes creep to occur in the metal matrix. This internal stress is a result of the difference in the thermal expansion coefficient between the matrix and the fiber.

This effect is particularly marked for composites containing high modulus graphite fibers, that have a very low or negative thermal expansion coefficient. The net result of this creep is a permanent change in length of a structure after cycling. Whether this change in length is expansion or contraction seems to depend on the temperature extremes of the thermal cycle. The higher the temperature achieved in the thermal cycle the greater the observed permanent contraction.

2.4 Corrosion Behavior

The corrosion behavior of most aluminum based metal matrix composites seems to be about the same as their matrix alloy. This, however, is not the case with aluminum-graphite composites, where presumably galvanic corrosion is generated by the difference in electromechanical potential between the two electrically conducting materials. The degree of corrosion occurring depends on the area of the exposed fiber bundles. Once initiated, corrosion is rapid and disintegration of the structure occurs due to the formation of a voluminous aluminum hydroxide in the corrosion cracks, (Fig. 7) so that the cracks are progressively opened by the growth of the hydroxide.

3.0 CONCLUSIONS

1. Compared to aluminum alloys, metal matrix composites offer increased specific stiffness, which will result in weight savings in buckling critical situations.
2. Unidirectional metal matrix composites offer a combination of high transverse thermal conductivity and low longitudinal thermal expansion coefficients, which offer advantages for structures requiring dimensional stability.
3. Metal matrix composites in their present stage of development have low toughness compared to aluminum alloys and are not yet able to take advantage of the toughness of the metallic matrix.

4. Discontinuous reinforcements such as silicon carbide whiskers result in almost isotropic mechanical properties even after hot working processes. These processes result in considerable whisker alignment.
5. Aluminum-graphite composites suffer marked local corrosion in seawater if the graphite fibers are exposed to the environment.

TABLE 2

Longitudinal Compression Properties of Al-SiC + 20% Whisker Tubing
(76.2 mm long, 17.8 mm wall thickness)

	0.2% CYS MPa	Buckling Stress MPa	Elastic Modulus GPa
Al 2024 + 20% SiC - As Extruded	336	509	120
Al 2024 + 20% SiC - T6	498	600	--
Al 6061 + 20% SiC - As Extruded	251	356	--
Al 6061 + 20% SiC - T6	373	515	--

TABLE 3

Physical Properties of Metal Matrix Composites

Material	Direction	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion m/m ^o K at 293 ^o K	Thermal Conductivity Watts/m ^o C	Density gm/cc
Al - 55% Al ₂ O ₃	L	6.7		3.3
	T		44.5	
Al - 30% Graphite GY70	L	5.6		2.49
	T		49.6	
Al 7075 - 27% SiC Whiskers	L	9.13		2.88
	T		73.5	
Al (pure) - 27% SiC Whiskers	T		126.5	2.77
Al 6061 - 48% SiC Fibers	L	5.8		2.95
	T		85.5	
Al 6061 Only		22.7	165.4	2.7

TABLE 1
TENSILE PROPERTIES OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

Material and Condition	Orientation to Fiber Axis	0.2% YS MPa	UTS MPa	E1%	Charpy Value (J)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)
Al - 2% Li + Al ₂ O ₃ (55%) As Received T6	0	373	373	0.2	4.2	237
	90	209	234	0.6	1.6	151
Al 7075 + 27% SiC Whiskers Extrusion T6 Condition	0	524	524*	-	0.7	127
	90	423	437*	-		117
	Sheet as Rolled	0	-	608	0.7	132
	Sheet T6	0	-	555	0.8	139
Al 6061 + 20% SiC Whiskers As Extruded T6	0	192	286	2	0.8	
	0	368	415	1		
Al 2024 + 20% SiC Whiskers As Extruded	0	271	410	2	1.4	120
					1.7	
Al 201 + 30% Graphite (GY70)	0		490	-	3.3	200
	90		17	0	0.4	31.7
Al 6061 + 48% SiC Fibers	0	479	600	0.8	20.2	20.2
	90	43	43	0.2	0.7	64

*Broke in loading hole

FIG. 1 FRACTURE SURFACE OF AL 55% ALUMINA SHOWING GOOD FIBER -MATRIX BONDING.

FIG. 2 AL 30% SIC WHISKER COMPOSITE EXTRUDED 10:1 AND HOT ROLLED 90%.
NO BREAKDOWN OF THE WHISKER -MATRIX INTERFACE IS EVIDENT.

FIG. 3 FRACTURE SURFACE OF AL 6061 REINFORCED WITH 20% OF SiC WHISKERS,
WHISKER PULL-OUT IS EVIDENT.

FIG.4. ALUMINUM- 48% SILICON CARBIDE FIBER COMPOSITE, FIBERS ARE COATED WITH CARBON AND SHOW POOR ADHESION TO THE MATRIX.

FIG. 5. TRANSVERSE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY OF SELECTED METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES.

FIG. 6. COEFFICIENT OF THERMAL EXPANSION OF ALUMINUM REINFORCED WITH SILICON CARBIDE WHISKERS AND FIBERS

FIG. 7 ALMINUM-GRAPHITE (GY 70) COMPOSITE AFTER IMMERSION FOR 500 HOURS IN SEAWATER.